
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ANTHROPOLOGY OF RELIGION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7977337>

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Abstract.

Religion is nature, society, man and his mind, purpose and destiny of life, which is outside the environment that directly surrounds humanity and in the same era that created it, restored the right, true and just way of life to people. Maslak is a doctrine of vision by expressing faith and trust in divine power. We have commented on a number of questions such as the origin of religion, the world, man, creatures, and the purpose of human existence. From the point of view of secular science, religion is one of the social changes that appeared at a certain stage of the historical development of human society. This worldview is formed based on the demands of society in a certain historical period and leader. The great thinker Abu Nasr Farabi considered religion as one of 2 independent ways to reach the truth along with philosophy. According to Farabi, the prophets in the form of symbols explained the proofs of philosophical issues.

Key words.

the concept of religion, faith, Zoroastrism, Islam, Buddhism, Judaism, Christianity, society.

Introduction. The new stage of the development of religious studies is connected with the work of the English anthropological school, which studies the first forms of religion. These studies led E. Taylor to the concept of animism in 1867. Taylor, as well as Spencer and Lebbok, viewed religion as “primitive epistemology, the fruit of primitive human mental activity, which arose as a result of misinterpretation of elementary human experiences (sleep, death, etc).” According to Taylor, the cult was a product of religious views and appeared later. Using the concept of the evolution of the history of religion, Taylor and Spencer believe that there is a “period before religion”. One of the characteristic features of

the modern reality is that the influence of scientific thinking on all spheres of society is increasing sharply, its role as a factor of social development is increasing. The achievements of science in the 20 th century are indeed: is great. It becomes a direct productive force, allowing a deeper understanding of the secrets of human nature. In the current situation, the theoretical achievements of scientific religiosity require a reconsideration of the relationship to religion and believers, taking into account the ideological and practical work of religious organizations in our country. From primitive forms of religion to clan, tribe and national religions, there are social, epistemological (theoretical knowledge) and psychological roots of the emergence and development of world religions. The concept of religion. Philosophical essence of religion and religious belief. The concept of religion represents a multifaceted, complex and conflicting social phenomenon. The word "religion" entered the Uzbek language from the Arabic language and means trust, belief. Faith is also an Arabic word meaning deep and firm belief. Religion and religious belief have been the main topic of philosophy since the beginning of science. Philosophers were divided into idealists and materialists in relation to religion and knowledge of the world. Using the dialectical method of knowledge, secular theology has provided a detailed analysis of the epistemological and social roots of religion, its essence, origin and development. The psychological root of religion depends on the characteristics of the human psyche, which makes it possible for the world to be perceived in the human mind. These mental states of the believer, which include rational and emotional elements, create the conditions and opportunities for the emergence of religious self-awareness and self-awareness. They can be realized under the influence of certain social, primarily negative factors. These factors are the reason for the emergence of various negative feelings. Psychological and epistemological roots of religion are closely connected with each other. In this, the elements of understanding the psyche of a person with the help of the mind and emotional-volitional feeling apply.

Philosophical essence of religion. The scientific foundations of the study of the causes of the emergence of religion are described in secular theology as follows. When explaining the emergence of religious concepts, doctrines and ideas, it is necessary to take into account the conditions of human development. Attitude to religion in Uzbekistan. In the current situation, scientific religiosity required a review of the relations to religion and believers, taking into account the theoretical achievements and the ideological and practical work of religious organizations in our country. Such a need requires an objective assessment of the social relations of religious organizations to the current social system. All this is due to the demand of

the time and with a sense of future responsibility, to determine the level of religiosity of the population in our republic, to correctly interpret the role of religious people and religious associations in society, and to restore the universal principles of relations between religion and the state, religion and religious is an unbiased approach to institutional problems. This movement has a multilateral nature and is reflected in the internal and external policy of our independent republic.

Discussion and results.

Our republic is establishing extensive economic, social and cultural relations with all peace-loving countries of the East and West, regardless of their social system and religion. The increasing activity of religious organizations in social life can be seen as the strengthening of their place in the process of democracy. Taking into account the increasing social activity characteristic of religious organizations, it is necessary to increase the activity of the individual in two directions - in social life and worldview. It is becoming a habit that religious organizations openly and positively approach the real reality in social directions. This can be witnessed by the objective relations and positive evaluation of religious organizations in the life of our republic. The social activities of some religious organizations are important in this. Anthropology of religion is the study of religion in relation to other social institutions and the comparison of religious beliefs and practices across cultures. Early Greek philosophers. In the great Western epics "Odyssey" and "Eliad" written by Homer (700 BC), one can find myths about gods and heroes that are understood with indirect ideas about their nature and character.²³⁵

The Greek philosopher Anixamander (610-546 BC) introduced the concept of a single, formless, indivisible and boundless essence (apeiron) for the first time. From this source, devoid of definition and description, arise all like and opposite, i.e. interrelated things (i.e. hot and cold, dry and wet). On the other hand, "apeiron", which is considered as the owner of absolute power and the cause of causes, is equated with the only God. Indian philosophers point out that the above ideas are presented in the Upanishads in the same form and time. They considered Brahman to be the all-powerful, creator of all things, without description, and raised him to the level of God. At the same time, the first Daoist philosophers in China put forward the idea of the "dao" as the creator of all pairs (Yin and Yang) and free from definition that returns to itself. The Greek philosopher Xenophanes (580-490 BC) himself he criticizes the ideas of polytheism that flourished in the era and

²³⁵ Hillary Rodrigues. John S.Harding. Introduction to study of religion.- USA, Routledge, 2009

supports the idea of a single omnipotent power. He points out how the gods of the Thracians (an ancient Indo-European people who lived in the Balkan Peninsula) were blue-eyed and red-haired, and the gods of the Ethiopians were black and snub-nosed, as a result of how people depicted their gods in their images. The Greek historian Herodotus described the religious beliefs of other cultures. Despite a number of errors and omissions in his works, he recorded that some Greek beliefs, gods and rituals were borrowed from Greek culture. The works of Xenophanes and Herodotus were carried out on the origin of myths and religion, the periodic transformation of religious beliefs and practices and the spread to other regions and the enrichment of local religious views. Serves as increased initial research.²³⁶

Aristotle (384-322), a famous disciple of Plato (427-347 BC), talked about how a tyrant becomes righteous and he connect this situation with the realization of one's own weakness. Aristotle used the concept of "metaphysics" for the first time. In the work "Physics", which gave him the name "first teacher", there was talk about "metaphysics", in the words of Aristotle, "first philosophy". Aristotle's "first philosophy" or "metaphysics" included the following components: ontology (the study of existence), theology (the study of God, gods or theology), concrete knowledge that is, clear or uncontroversial knowledge about the world By the middle ages of Europe, the "intellectual heritage" left by Plato, Aristotle and other Greek philosophers continued to "live" in harmony with the religious traditions of the Western world. Western philosophical tradition has been influenced by worldviews formed by Abrahamic religions (Judaism, Christianity and Islam). These religions are based on the divine teachings of Abraham and the prophets who came after him, sent by the Almighty, known as Yahweh, Allah, or simply God.

In addition, in *The Guide to the Perplexed*, Maimonides noted that Aristotle and a number of Muslim philosophers greatly influenced the formation of his views. Among the Muslim scholars, the author of more than 450 monographs, thinker and physician Ibn Sina mentioned him with special respect. In turn, the works of Maimonides greatly influenced the work of Christian theologians Thomas Aquinas (Thomas Aquinas, 1225-1274) and John Duns Scotus (John Duns Scotus, 1266-1308). Thomas Aquinas is regarded as the most influential theologian, and his collection of rational opinions on every issue of the Catholic faith, "Summa

²³⁶ Dinshunoslik asoslari (o'quv qo'11anma) / Mualliflar jamoasi. — T. «Toshkent islom universiteti nashriyot matbaa birlashmasi», 2013.

Theology", is considered very popular. Through his works, Aquinas reincarnated the scholastic tradition that began in the ninth century and tried to harmonize Aristotle's philosophical views with theology. Modern Western philosophy.

Modern Western philosophy is associated with the work of the French philosopher René Descartes (1596-1650), who contributed greatly to the development of Cartesianism or analytical geometry, because I think (Cogito ergo sum) became famous. Descartes emphasizes the existence of Rene Descartes as a thinker, and prefers to use a systematic way of thinking to develop his understanding of the world. Another of his merits is that he proposes to use his method (which he claims is the most reliable) to justify the existence of God. To find the truth the method of using rational thinking as the main tool has become the foundation of the modern Western philosophical tradition. Until Descartes, there was no separate scientific and logical approach to resolve the gap between faith and reason.

Immanuel Kant (1724-1804) was one of the Enlightenment leaders who encouraged the growth of the role of logic and thinking in Western philosophy. Kant proved that our understanding and understanding are formed through our mind. The human mind filters all our emotional experiences of the world and limits our ability to know the truth. At this time, although there is no way to prove it, Christian theologian-thinker (scholastics) always asked questions about "how angels play through the eye of a needle, about spiritual beings (angels, spirits, demons) occupying heaven" who are engaged in deep reflection on. Regarding this way of thinking, Kant considers that "soul, god and similar metaphysical concepts are matters that cannot be understood by human mind and human experience." Therefore, it is impossible to reach the meaning of the concepts of "god" or "angel", if there are such beings, to have complete knowledge about them. Some Western philosophers who followed the above views of Kant concluded "the metaphysical views advanced by religions have no value for thinking because they do not lead to reasonable and satisfactory knowledge."

Of course, one thing is known that when some group repeatedly voices a view that is not rational or illogical, the other group will follow it involuntarily. The development of scientific methods such as "Occam's razor" (Occam's razor, the principle of economic thinking) simultaneously with its main principles put religious and metaphysical views aside. It was concluded that it will not be implemented. This made conflicts between philosophy and religion stronger. Ludwig Wittgenstein (Ludwig Wittgenstein, 1889-1951) is one of the few philosophers who tried to bridge this divide. Although he recognized the

limitations of human ability to express emotional experience, at the same time, he did not reject the possibilities of religious experience.

Wittgenstein focused on “language games” or the use of language for various purposes. According to him, parables and legends are fundamentally different from the language of liturgy, theology or historical sources. In response to the allegorical (figurative) method put forward by Philo almost two thousand years ago, Wittgenstein's position was such that ideas such as “the existence of God” in religious texts do not correspond to the views expressed on the basis of philosophical arguments²³⁷. Wittgenstein states that if a person kisses a portrait of a loved one, it is not considered a kiss on the face, even kissing or saying “I love you” is a sign of love. However each such action may represent a similar relationship involving a different context and purpose. Besides, religious actions and religious language can belong to different categories of human behavior and serve different purposes than philosophical expressions. Accordingly, it is unwise to keep official restrictions on only one language. A brief historical study of the relationship between religion and philosophy in the West showed that it was not different from the views of the first Greek thinkers (Socrates, Plato, Aristotle) who freely reacted to metaphysical concepts.²³⁸

When the principles of Judaism, Christianity and Islam became the dominant worldview in the Middle East and West, philosophy became a form of apologetic (defending religious beliefs) study of religious doctrines based on rational thoughts. One of its great exponents is the Catholic theologian Thomas Aquinas, and this kind of philosophical approach still has meaning and essence as theology. At the same time, the gap between theology (metaphysics) and philosophy that has arisen since the “age of enlightenment” is recognized as one of the “unfortunate events”. As a result, philosophy was equated with the exact and natural sciences, while metaphysics was absorbed into scientific hypothesis and theory science.

Formation of religion in the East. From the fifth century BC, Eastern thinkers began to make deep observations on issues such as consciousness and matter, the nature of particles, and the limits of rational thought. Thinkers of the Vaisheshika school in India studied the structure of the atomic particles that form the basis of matter. They were also interested in, as the Greek geometer Euclid said, if atoms have a certain size, what length, height, or weight that size has. We can say that such questions are still on the minds of physicists. Siddhartha Guatama (Buddha)

²³⁷ **The Guide to the Perplexed World Digital Library. Retrieved 22 January 2013.**

²³⁸ Raximdjano, D.P. Dinshunoslikka kirish [Matn]: o'quv qo'llanma / D.Raximdjano, O.Ernazarov. — Toshkent: «O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati» nashriyoti, 2018. — 304 b.

pointed out that it is impossible for thinking to depend on supernatural content, but rather emphasizes that existence has a changing nature. In other words, although the present is different from the past, in fact, today is shaped by the past. Metaphorically speaking, the “things” we perceive in our imagination are like the flame of a candle, the flame that burns the wick does not appear to affect the body of the candle, but actually burns the candle.

In this sense, denying the process of change is a mistake and leads us to suffering. Gautama's ideas were later developed by the Buddhist philosopher who tried to demonstrate by logical argument that nothing can arise or exist by itself. It was further developed by Nagarjuna (second century AD). In the Muslim East, Aristotle's idea was reinterpreted in a strictly monotheistic spirit, sometimes agreeing with (or disputing) Plato's principles (eg al-Kindi, al-Farabi). The emergence of philosophy (al-falasifa) took place under the influence of ancient models. Muslim philosophers, while not rejecting the divine nature of existence, divided the sciences into a theological science based on written narrations (ulum naqliyyah). And those who divided existence into a rational science based on rational interpretation. Al-philosophy in this sense is close to the science of the word. In the science of speech, the superiority of Aristotle's dialectic can be felt. Central Asia also gave the world a series of famous philosophers belonging to different schools (schools of al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, al-Farabi). The service of these philosophers to world philosophy is that the separation of philosophy and theology is justified in their works. In this, philosophy is imagined as “the basis of knowledge of the whole being” - ideas and Western European philosophers came to this conclusion only a hundred years later. In many democratic societies of the world, issues of freedom of religion and conscience are regulated by a number of regulations. In this context, a number of national and secular people occupy an important place in the material and spiritual life of people. For example:

1. The religion of Zoroastrism arose in the 7th-6th century BC. Its founder was Zarathustra. Judging by the conclusions of the last study, Central Asia, in particular, was the homeland of Khorezm. It is distributed in Central Asia, Iran, Afghanistan, Azerbaijan and several countries of the Near Middle East. Holy book - “Avesta”.

2. Buddhism - (named after Buddha), Buddhism is one of the most widespread religions in the world. It appeared in India in the 6th-5th centuries BC. The founder is Buddha. It appeared in the countries of Central Asia, South-East Asia and the Far East. The holy book of Buddhism is “Tripitaka”.

3. Judaism is one of the oldest religions spread mainly among Jews. It arose in Palestine at the beginning of the 1st millennium BC. The Torah was revealed to Prophet Moses on Mount Sinai, and it embodies scientific and practical rulings. The Holy Book "Tanah"

4. Christianity. Christianity is one of the most widespread religions in the world. Christianity appeared among the Jews living in the eastern part of the Roman Empire in the second half of the 1st century. According to the Bible, Jesus Christ (Lisus Christ) is the founder of Christianity, and the Holy Book is the Bible.

5. Islam is the youngest religion among world religions, and in terms of the number of believers, it ranks second after Christianity. The number of believers in this religion is increasing year by year. Islam appeared in the Arabian Peninsula (now Saudi Arabia) in the 7th century. This island means "Jazirat al-Arab" in Arabic, that is, the peninsula of the Arabs. Turkic peoples and Iranians call it "Arabia". The word "Islam" means the following:

1. Obedience and submission.
2. Sincerity and health from various disasters.

3. Peace and safety. Islam means to submit to him with the belief that Allah is the only one, to obey him and to be devoted to him with all one's heart and to believe in the religious faith commanded by Allah. Obedience to God: A person who does and follows the prophets sent by God is called a Muslim (Muslim-faithful). The emergence of Islam is directly related to the socio-economic situation in the Arabian Peninsula at the end of the 6th century and the beginning of the 7th century. So, what was this socio-economic situation? First of all, the Arabs are divided into large and small tribes and clans. This division became the main factor of constant wars between them. These wars only caused destruction. Second, the neighboring countries - the Byzantine Empire, Sassanid Iran and Abyssinia - took advantage of the lack of political unity in the Arabian Peninsula and constantly attacked this country and troubled the Arabs. Thus, in the 7th century, the time demanded that the Arabs establish a single state. It was necessary to solve the task of political unification, creation of a single Arab state, uniting the power of the people to fight against foreign invaders and ending internal wars. At that time, such a political unification could only be achieved through monotheism, only under the slogan of one god. In the 6th century, polytheistic religions existed in Arabia. At the same time, it is worth noting that polytheism was emerging and the new system-feudal society, which was gradually opening its way to development, did not meet the social and political requirements constitutes the objective conditions for the emergence of religion. Muhammad (pbuh) is considered the

founder of Islam. Regarding the emergence of the religion of Islam, in the religious tradition based on Islamic sources, it was considered a divine event, a teaching sent by God to guide people to the right path. In the interpretation of Islam, initially Jews and Christians believed in the same God that Muslims believed in. This God, that is, Allah, sent prophets and messengers to people, but people violated the teachings of the prophets. That is why God chose Muhammad as the last messenger to mankind, and revealed his word - the Qur'an to him. Muhammad first called his countrymen, and then all Arabs, to abandon the worship of many tribal gods and to believe in the only God - Allah, to live a righteous life, and to do good deeds in this world in order to enter Paradise in the next world. According to the Qur'an (SURAH, AYT), Abraham (A.S.), the grandfather of Arabs and Jews, was the first to believe in God. So, Islam is not a completely new faith, but a religion that was revealed to Abraham.

Conclusion.

Anthropology is the study of human phenomena, so we must take into account both noble and ancient societies, as well as our own time. This science deals with the development of human species, ethnic diversity, cultural diversity, social customs, beliefs, transformation processes, etc. Anthropological studies demonstrate the cultural diversity that has existed throughout history, which has fostered respect and tolerance for different beliefs and cultures. Religious scholars are representatives of various fields of science and study religions from the point of view of their own particular field of science is studied. Therefore, it is natural that there are some differences between them. For example, scientists dealing with the history of religion studied the history of religions from a chronological perspective. Another group of scholars studied religions according to their regions of origin and spread. For example, Joakim Wach divides religions into "religions with a founder", "traditional religion", and Gustav Menshing divides them into "national religions" and "world religions". Annemarie Schimmel divides religions into three categories - tribal, national, and world religions. At the same time, some researchers present the following classification: Sacramental (relying on religious rituals and images) religion, Prophetic religion, Mystical (spiritual) religion.

Islamic scholars have divided religions into "true" and "false" or divine religions that rely on revelation, and natural religions that do not rely on revelation. Muslim researchers such as Ibn Hazm (d. 456/1064) and Shahristani (d. 548/1183) used the words "milal" for true religions and "nihal" for false religions. The regional approach is also widely used in the classification of religions, and its distinctive feature is the study of the influence and interaction of one religion in the

region with another religion, or the study of the similarities and differences between the religions of different regions. Religions are classified based on the following factors.

1. Classification of African, Asian, European, American and Australian religions according to their spread on the continents. However, this is not a very appropriate classification, because there are religions that are spread over several continents. In particular, Islam and Christianity exist on almost all continents. Also, in some continents, almost the majority of the population believes in one religion, while there are also representatives of other religions that form a minority. For example, Christianity is more common in Europe, and Islam is more common in Africa compared to America. Religions of Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism, Confucianism, and Shintoism are mixed on the Asian continent. Sometimes a religion that originated in one continent is widespread in another continent. For example, although Christianity originated in Palestine, it mainly spread outside of the Asian continent.

2. Classification according to the geographical region into Eastern religions and Western religions. It is a broad geographical classification that reflects political and cultural differences similar to the division of the world into poles. Eastern religions include Hinduism, Buddhism, Confucianism, Shintoism, Daoism and other Far Eastern religions. Western religions include Judaism, Christianity and Islam. In fact, Islam cannot be called the religion of the West or the East. Geographically, it originated in the East, and it is also widespread in Western countries. Judaism and Christianity are actually Eastern religions that originated in the Near East and spread widely in Western countries.

3. According to political regions, ancient religions are classified as Mesopotamian religions, Syrian religions, Asia Minor or Onadoli religions, and Persian religions.

4. According to the regions of the country, religions are classified as Palestinian religions, Arabian Peninsula religions, Mexican religions, Indian religions, Chinese religions, Japanese religions. Geographical classification is a convenient scientific classification in many cases where it is not possible to clearly define the religions of some regions, such as the religions of the Far East, according to their religious theme. For example, if Judaism, Christianity, and Islam can be summarized on the basis of monotheism, Far Eastern religions cannot be summarized on the basis of a single religious concept. In this case, we refer to geographical classification as a solution to the problem.

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